

Some Reflections on Ways to Bring About a Permanently Sustainable World Agriculture

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Is an ecological approach necessary to achieve a sustainable world agriculture? I believe the answer is "yes" and that this, in its turn, implies agricultural techniques based on the biological requirements of soil, plants, and animals (including Man). The aim of such techniques is optimum production rather than maximum production and entails a system of farming and gardening which is primarily "organic".

In recent years an increasing number of scientists, and practical cultivators, have come to share this view, but there is still a very widely held opinion in official circles that intensive chemical farming provides the only hope of feeding the expanding world population and has therefore to be accepted whether we like it or not. To me it seems probable that the exact opposite could prove to be the case, and that it is an alternative and largely organic agriculture that will be forced upon us whether we like it or not. This is because, as is becoming increasingly apparent, the days of the former are numbered. One reason is the enormous demand on the world's non-renewable resources of energy, made by our Western life-style in general and modern farming techniques in particular. Another is that modern methods are putting strains on the biota which is causing it to collapse.

Thus it is only common sense to look at alternatives, and in all seriousness study their potential viability. It is not yet, however, generally accepted that the days of our present methods and behaviour are numbered. Even where it is, it is too often regarded as a long term problem which must not be allowed to obscure the immediate objective, namely the need to increase quantitative food production now. Here it is argued that organic farming is less efficient, that it has to rely on re-cycling which is wasteful, so that, were it to be adopted, world food production would inevitably be lower, particularly production of protein at a time when what we need is to produce ever more per acre.

To this I would like to point out three things :

1. A common view among nutritionists today is that the amount of protein (especially animal protein) hitherto thought to be required by man has been greatly over-estimated (organic farmers have found this also to be true for livestock).
2. There need be little loss in re-cycling if we did not waste so much.

3. Certainly we need to produce more per acre. Unfortunately the yardstick of modern economics is to measure efficiency by production per *man*.

For over half the world this yardstick makes no sense whatsoever—in rich, highly industrialised western countries it has been possible in the past (it is increasingly less so) to make out a case for replacing human labour by high capital-cost machinery. Elsewhere in the world, circumstances require nearly the exact opposite. The measurement of efficiency then becomes (and will have, eventually, to apply to the "west" too) production per *unit of land*.

The key to success for this is not imported high capital-cost technology - so often excessively violent in operation, and which appears to deify giantism - but "appropriate", human scale, technology (as advocated by the late Dr. Schumacher) utilizing, as far as possible, local resources and able to cater for the needs of regional communities.

In any case labour-intensive small units, in which the T.L.C. factor can play a part (Tender Loving Care), will always be able to produce spectacularly more per acre than large mechanised farms.

When the inevitable change in western life-style takes place, I predict that we shall find it easier than now to feed the world population because western nations will presumably have become less gluttonous (and consequently probably also be healthier)!

We still hear, though less frequently than we used to, the argument that there is no scientific basis for advocating exclusive use of organic manures, such as FYM and compost, because "there is absolutely no difference between a plant nutrient contained in organic materials and the same nutrient in inorganic chemical form". There may be no chemical, or other easily analysable, difference, but as Dr. Dhar's work, among others, has clearly shown there is a demonstrable functional difference—to give one example—anything having an effect on root distribution may have an effect on plant nutrition because it will influence the volume of soil explored. Thus good soil structure in depth, such as is obtained in a biologically active soil, can improve productivity simply by increasing the depth of soil exploited for water and nutrients. There is now well documented scientific evidence that fertilizer concentrations of N and P have an influence on localised root branching¹. They induce

it at the expense of deep rooting exploration. This could well lead to luxury uptakes of N and P linked to inadequate uptake of other nutrients. There are implications in this for nutrient unbalance in the crop and thereby some risk of nutrient unbalance in the animals and humans feeding upon it. If root activity is a factor in the development and maintenance of soil structure, there are also implications in this for the overall pattern of soil development.

In a biologically active soil, which implies one adequately provided with organic matter and natural rock minerals, the latter are released as the plant wants them, moreover the roots are presented with a complete diet from which they can pick and choose. Plants are highly selective in such circumstances, hence the value of some of the deep rooting weeds (which the organic farmer calls herbs when he sows them deliberately). Normal chemical fertilizers, apart from the disadvantage just mentioned are far too simple. A plant's mineral requirements are many times wider in range. By giving only two or three which stimulate bulk growth, others, equally important, are exhausted, or locked up in the immediate neighbourhood of the rhizosphere, thus leading, as already mentioned, to unbalanced nutrition of the plant and often, through their solubility, to serious environmental pollution.

Plant nutrients do not, as was once taught, all have to be reduced to simple inorganic solutions in order to be absorbed. Plants can ingest quite complex organic molecules, unbroken. The history of D.D.T. provides irrefutable evidence for this. So do such symbiotic mechanisms as mycorrhizal association, whereby the plant may well derive some nutrient equivalent to vitamins in animal nutrition.

A possible additional factor for which, I readily admit, there is at present no scientific proof but which seems to me to provide an interpretation consistent with many observations, is that, in nature's food-chains, a plant's normal method of mineral intake is not direct, but second-hand, the mineral plant-foods being, as it were, by-products of the activity of the soil micro-flora and other members of the soil population.

Such by-products have a far more complex and comprehensive formula than N, P and K and moreover are living substances. Inorganic chemicals are inert. A food-chain is not only a material circuit but also an energy circuit. Soil fertility has been defined as the capacity of soil to receive, store and transmit energy. A substance may be the same chemically but very different as a conductor of living energy. The hypothesis is that the energy manifesting in birth, growth, reproduction, death, decay and rebirth, can only flow through channels composed of living cells, and that when the flow is interrupted by inert matter it can be short-circuited with consequent damage to some part of the food-chain, not necessarily where the block occurred. The Anthroposophical Society's Research establishment at Dornach in Switzerland has provided some evidence which appears to support such a view.

I would like to see much more research undertaken in this field.

Now I want to put forward what I believe our aims should be in evolving a sustainable agriculture and give my own interpretation of biological husbandry. In doing the latter I recognise that any examples I give are taken from my personal experience of farming and gardening in the Northern Hemisphere, and on soils mainly of ex-glacial origin but in my many travels I have seen the principle underlying the techniques I describe, successfully applied in a wide variety of climates, conditions and soils, including some of the highly vulnerable tropical soils, where modern western technology can be, and has on occasion been, disastrous. While techniques must vary according to local conditions the principle is quite simple. It consists of recognising that the soil is a complex living entity and treating it as such.

The criteria for a sustainable agriculture can be summed up in one word—permanence, which means adopting techniques that maintain soil fertility indefinitely; that utilise, as far as possible, only renewable resources; that do not grossly pollute the environment, and that foster life energy (or if preferred biological activity) within the soil and throughout the cycles of all the involved food-chains.

This is what biological husbandry sets out to attempt—with an increasing degree of understanding and success among its practitioners. Throughout the world, as a result of their own experience, these cultivators sincerely believe that they can offer a genuine and viable alternative agriculture, capable of solving many of the problems of mankind. This possibility, as well as the need for it, is becoming, as I mentioned earlier, increasingly recognised in academic and scientific circles.

As a result of this, much valuable practical research is at present going on in some European countries to adapt and improve traditional biological techniques and tools to render them better suited to present day needs, both in the west and in the Third World.

I am often asked how, in a broad sense, I define "Organic Farming" as opposed to conventional farming. Though I prefer the term "biological husbandry" because of its emphasis on life, the short answer is *Balance*; however, I think it is necessary to amplify a little.

Contrary to the views held by some, I am sure that the techniques of "organic farming" cannot be imprisoned in a rigid set of rules. They depend essentially on the outlook of the farmer. Without a positive and ecological approach it is not possible to farm organically. The approach of the modern conventional farmer is negative, narrow and fragmentary, and consequently produces imbalance. His attitude to "pests" and "weeds", for example, is to regard them as enemies to be killed—if possible exterminated. When he attacks them with lethal chemicals he seldom gives a thought to the effect this may have on the food supply or habitat of

other forms of wildlife among whom he has many more friends than foes. The predatory insects and the insectivorous birds are obvious examples.

The attitude of the organic farmer, who has trained himself to think ecologically, is different. He tries to see the living world as a whole. He regards so-called pests and weeds as part of the natural pattern of the biota, probably necessary to its stability and permanence, to be utilized rather than attacked. Throughout his operations he endeavours to achieve his objective by co-operating with natural agencies in place of relying on man-made substitutes. He studies what appear to be nature's rules—as manifested in a healthy wilderness—and attempts to adapt them to his own farm needs, instead of flouting them. One of the first things he will notice about a natural eco-system, such as a wilderness or a natural forest, is balance and stability. The innumerable different species of fauna and flora that go to make up such a community, achieve, as a result of their interdependence, whether in co-operation or competition, collective immortality. Seldom, if ever, is any species eliminated; seldom, if ever, does any species multiply to pest proportions.

Thus the organic farmer, if he has a crop badly attacked by some pest, let us say, (and this can happen, even to organic farmers!) recognises that this is a symptom of imbalance in his local environment, and he first looks to see if some faulty technique of his own has been responsible—often it has. This does not mean that he can always avoid emergency remedial measures but these he employs only when there is a real emergency, not as a routine. He strives instead to bring about biological balance, and it is remarkable the extent to which the organic farmers and growers do in fact achieve this. I could give you several examples, but one must suffice.

Some years ago a large scale organic commercial grower of my acquaintance, growing vegetables, fruit and flowers, was visited by a team of scientists from Cambridge University—they included plant pathologists and entomologists. They knew it was an unsprayed holding and they came looking for disease and pests. They found isolated examples of everything they expected to find, but, as they put it, they failed to find a single case of crop damage.

Besides biological balance, the ecologically minded organic farmer takes note of, and tries to apply, other apparent biological rules. For example nature's diversity of species he adapts through rotations, under-sowing, and avoiding monoculture of crops or animals. Nature's habit of filtering sunlight and rain through some form of protective soil cover he adapts by such practices as cover-cropping and mulching. Top soil on the top appears to be nature's plan. Organic matter is always deposited on the surface. It is left to the earthworms and some insects to take it below. The organic farmer also puts his compost and farmyard manure on, or very near, the surface, and

in carrying out mechanical cultivations keeps soil-inversion to a minimum, the tine cultivator being preferred to the plough.

Nature's highly efficient re-cycling system ensures provision of living food for all organisms in the food chain from soil bacteria and fungi to large fauna; the organic farmer therefore lays great stress on the conversion and return to the soil of all organic residues. His aim is to feed and to assist proliferation of the soil population and to leave it to feed the crop.

Finally, and of equal importance, he notes, and tries to reproduce, the almost perfect structure of a biologically active soil which alone ensures the three most important characteristics of a fertile soil—good aeration, water-holding capacity, and free drainage.

It is quite astonishing the extent to which this all-important property of good soil is neglected in modern agriculture. Poor soil structure leads to imbalance between water and air in the pore spaces of the soil. Many apparent mineral or trace mineral deficiencies in the soil turn out to be oxygen deficiencies. When that is corrected the others disappear. In most agricultural soils there is really plenty of mineral plant food for the nutritional requirements of plants, even when continuously cropped, if their roots are allowed to exploit it downwards. The key to this is good soil structure which is greatly influenced by the activity of earthworms. The techniques of modern farming tend to destroy good structure in a number of ways, such as by the impaction of heavy implements, by carrying out cultivations in unsuitable weather conditions, and by failure to provide sufficient organic food and/or a suitable lime status for the earthworm population (or its equivalent in tropical soils).

All these faults are the outcome of failure to think ecologically—they are symptoms of a degree of fragmentation in our approach to the living world which has become a real threat to our survival. Throughout biological evolution, starting from single celled organisms right up to the complexity of rain forests, the process has been characterised by increasing diversity among species, lengthening of the food chains, and progressive enrichment of the environment. For the first time in the history of the planet the actions of modern man appear to be putting this process into reverse. Whole species of fauna and flora are being eliminated, the food-chains are becoming shorter, and the environment progressively impoverished. It only takes a little imagination to picture what could happen if the trend continues.

What are we going to do about it? This is the real challenge, and in my view it is one of education.

It is urgently necessary that the broadest possible aspect of ecology should form part of the regular curriculum of all schools, starting at the primary stage. The trouble is we have first to teach the teachers, and here, I think, we must be agreed on what we want to teach. There are two motivations

behind an ecological approach—one is based on self interest, however enlightened, i. e. when consideration for other species is taught solely because on that depends the survival of our own. This approach can still lead to harmful fragmentation.

The other motivation springs from a sense that the biota is a whole, of which we are a part, and that the other species which compose it and helped to create it, are entitled to existence in their own right. This is the wholeness approach and it is my belief that the survival of planet Earth depends on its wide acceptance.

If I am right, this means that we cannot escape from the ethical and spiritual values of life for they are part of wholeness. To ignore them and their implications would be to pursue another form of fragmentation.

Therefore, I hold that what we have to teach is the attitude defined by the late Aldo Leopold as "A Land Ethic". This requires that we extend the concept of Community to include all the species of life with which we share the planet. We must foster a reverence for all life, even that which we are forced to control, and we must, as Leopold put it—"Quit thinking about decent land use as solely an economic problem, but examine each question in terms of what is ethically and esthetically right, as well as what is economically expedient. A thing is right when it tends to preserve the integrity, stability and beauty of the biotic community. It is wrong when it tends otherwise".

Reference

1. M. C. DREW, Ag. Research Council, Letcome Laboratory Annual Report for 1975.